

Alberta's Renewable Energy Transition: Indigenous Participation, Challenges, and Policy Solutions

ABSTRACT

Although Alberta is known for its abundance of natural oil resources, it needs to transition to renewable energy due to its economic volatility, environmental destruction, and the negative impacts on the lives of Indigenous Peoples. This paper has several objectives: a) to describe the background and implications of Alberta's past energy use, as well as its path toward renewable energy; b) to explore current Indigenous partnerships in Alberta's renewable energy projects; c) to identify issues within the current modes of Indigenous participation and d) to present policy recommendations to address these issues with Indigenous partnerships in renewable energy projects. The methodology involves reviewing articles and analyzing statistics related to Alberta's fluctuating economy, and reviewing Canadian government sources on Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects. Current issues include legal and regulatory uncertainty resulting from the lack of clear implementation of UNDRIP and FPIC, as well as limited guidance and support for Indigenous Peoples throughout renewable energy projects. The limited guidance manifests in lack of support in selecting appropriate partnership models, assessing risk and value, ensuring full Indigenous consent, establishing standardized agreement templates, and accessing expert knowledge. Proposed policy recommendations focus on empowering Indigenous communities as key partners in renewable energy projects. These recommendations include embedding FPIC in approval procedures to ensure genuine consent; providing financial, technical, and advisory support during negotiations and implementation; and maintaining government oversight after project completion to ensure fair benefits and ongoing Indigenous community participation.

Keywords: Indigenous Peoples; Renewable Energy; UNDRIP; FPIC; Treaties; Energy Transition; Alberta; Canada

INTRODUCTION

The transition from traditional energy to renewable energy has become a global aspiration of the twenty-first century. While most countries have recognized the urgency of reducing greenhouse gas emissions, the pathway toward a just transition remains under debate (1). In Canada, this debate is especially relevant in the province of Alberta, where energy production is deeply tied to both its economy and the lives of Indigenous Peoples (2).

Alberta is heavily dependent on fossil fuel resources; in fact, oil and gas extraction accounts for around 21% of Alberta's GDP (3). This dependence exposes the province to economic volatility, and results in environmental and social consequences. Specifically, bitumen extraction from oil sands has led to water and air pollution, land degradation, and negative health impacts of surrounding Indigenous communities.

A significant gap in current discourse surrounding Alberta's renewable energy transition is how Indigenous Peoples can participate. Despite Alberta's growing renewable energy potential, the policy frameworks for renewable energy projects have yet to fully address Indigenous Peoples' participation in this emerging sector.

Moreover, although the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) enshrines the principle of Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC), Alberta’s implementation of this standard remains inconsistent and largely symbolic.

This paper argues that Alberta’s renewable energy transition must regard Indigenous Peoples as active decision-makers and co-owners, rather than a symbolic presence in the name of reconciliation. By embedding FPIC into project approval processes, providing Indigenous communities more technical and financial support, and ensuring continued government oversight after project implementation, Alberta can move toward a more sustainable energy future while strengthening ties with Indigenous communities.

The discussion proceeds in four parts: Section 1 outlines Alberta's energy use background and its path toward renewable energy; Section 2 reviews current Indigenous participation in renewable projects; Section 3 identifies major issues in Indigenous-involved renewable energy projects; and Section 4 concludes with policy recommendations to promote reconciliation through renewable energy.

BACKGROUND: ALBERTA’S PATH TO RENEWABLE ENERGY

This section will discuss reasons and implications of Alberta’s overdependence on fossil fuel resources, analyze Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030 as a model for energy transition, and review statistics on Alberta’s current progress in transitioning toward renewable energy.

Alberta’s Overdependence on Oil and Gas Resources

Alberta is heavily dependent on oil and gas resources, as it holds the third-largest proven oil reserves globally and is responsible for approximately 80% of Canada’s crude oil output and 70% of its natural gas production. Also, oil and gas extraction accounted for around 21% of Alberta's GDP (3).

Figure 1. WTI Oil Price vs Alberta Real GDP Growth (2005-2024). The correlation coefficient (r) between Alberta Real GDP Growth and WTI Oil Price is estimated to be approximately +0.7, indicating that WTI Oil Price and Alberta Real GDP Growth has a strong, positive linear relationship. It suggests that Alberta's Real GDP Growth tends to rise when West Texas Intermediate (WTI) oil prices rise, and tends to decrease when WTI oil prices fall.

Sharp declines in WTI oil prices coincide with recessions in Alberta, which occurred in 2009, 2015-2016 and 2020. Alberta's real GDP growth also follows economic rebounds, which occurred in 2010 and 2021-2022, after recessional periods. In sum, Alberta's economy fluctuates mostly depending on the price of natural resources and is currently vulnerable to global commodity price swings. Moreover, as oil is a non-renewable resource, it will eventually be depleted. Once oil production declines, Alberta could face severe economic consequences if it hasn't diversified.

Aside from causing economic instability, Alberta's oil industry also results in environmental and social problems. A significant social impact of the oil industry falls on the Indigenous Peoples. The oil industry has caused Indigenous communities to experience many health issues. Jesse Cardinal, from the indigenous led group Keepers of the Water claimed that "[the pollution] is so bad [Indigenous Peoples who live downstream] cannot open their windows because it hurts their lungs to breathe - especially at night" (4-6).

Lessons from Saudi Arabia's Energy Transition

Like Alberta, Saudi Arabia was previously over reliant on its oil industry—the oil and gas sector accounts for approximately 22.3% of Saudi Arabia's GDP and 55% of government revenue. To resolve this issue, Saudi Arabia developed Vision 2030 to foster economic diversification and transition toward renewable energy (7). Some goals of Vision 2030 include sourcing at least 50 percent of its power from renewable energy by 2030 and investing \$270 billion in renewable energy projects by 2030 (8).

According to the 2024 Annual Executive Summary, the benefits of the Vision 2030 include sustainable economic growth, job creation, and reduced environmental impact. Overall real GDP growth was approximately 3.9% since implementing Saudi Vision 2030, driven primarily by the non-oil economy (7). Also, inbound FDI (foreign direct investment) was \$20.69 billion as of the fourth quarter of 2024, which indicates increased international confidence and investment in diversified sectors (7). Furthermore, the unemployment rate decreased to 7% by the end of 2024, which exceeded the Vision 2030 target by six years (Saudi Vision 2030). Lastly, Saudi Arabia maintained a low annual inflation rate of 1.7% in 2024, which was among the lowest globally (7).

With Saudi Arabia's fruitful progress in transitioning to renewable energy, Alberta could benefit from pursuing a similar path. Currently, Alberta is already working toward a transition to renewable energy to address the issues outlined with oil overdependence. For instance, Alberta's share of coal in total electricity generation declined significantly from 25% in 2020 to just 2% in 2024, alongside the steady increase in renewable energy sources such as wind (9).

In conclusion, overdependence on oil resources has made Alberta heavily economically dependent on the price of oil, caused environmental degradation, and disruptions to Indigenous lifestyles. These issues reveal that

continued reliance on oil is unsustainable. As seen from Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030, Alberta would see great benefit in putting more effort and resources into accelerating its transition to renewable energy.

CURRENT INDIGENOUS PARTICIPATION IN ALBERTA’S RENEWABLE ENERGY

In the previous section, we established the urgent need for Alberta to transition to renewable energy. In this section, we examine why Indigenous participation is crucial in this transition, outline the current modes of Indigenous participation in projects, and highlight government-established organizations that support Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects.

Mandatory Consultation with Indigenous Peoples in Renewable Energy Projects

Figure 2. Alberta First Nations Treaty Map. Green areas indicate Alberta First Nations’ Treaty Lands No. 6, 7, and 8(10).

As shown in Figure 2, the majority of Alberta’s land is covered by treaty lands. Consultation with Indigenous Peoples is mandatory for all fishing, hunting, trapping, and land use activities (11). These domestic obligations align with FPIC (Free, Prior, and Informed Consent) of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) (11). Therefore, Indigenous Peoples must be involved in the transition towards renewable energy.

In Canada, the principles of UNDRIP intersect with constitutional protections under Section 35 of the Constitution Act, 1982, which recognizes and affirms the rights of Indigenous Peoples and treaty rights. When

Indigenous rights and lands are affected, the government has a “duty to consult and accommodate,” according to the Supreme Court of Canada. Although Section 35 does not explicitly mention “FPIC,” it is often regarded as the constitutional foundation for FPIC in Canadian domestic law (12).

The UNDRIP and FPIC, together with Section 35 of the Constitution Act of 1982, serve to illustrate the critical importance of meaningfully including and consulting with Indigenous Peoples when using Treaty Land during renewable energy projects in Alberta.

Types of Indigenous Involvement in Alberta’s Renewable Energy Projects

Currently, the involvement of Indigenous Peoples falls into two main categories: equity-holding and non-equity-holding.

- a. Non-equity holding: In the past, involvement was primarily non-equity-holding, with the majority being through Impact Benefit Agreements (IBAs). IBAs are usually negotiated privately between communities and project developers. They often set out agreed-upon mitigation measures for anticipated project impacts and compensation. They can also involve benefit sharing from development activities (13). In addition to IBAs, communities could generate revenue by receiving cash compensation, rent, employment, royalty agreements (permission to use creative work/natural resources for a small percentage of revenue), leases, or alternative legal structures to compensate the community for any land it provides to the project.
- b. Equity holding: Currently, there are three main types of equity partnerships for Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects: Minority (less than 50%), Co-ownership (50%), and Majority (more than 50%). In recent years, projects with equity-holding involvement have increased, but most of them involve minority ownership.

Organizations Supporting Indigenous Participation in Renewable Energy

The Alberta government has already established some organizations and programs to support Indigenous Peoples’ participation in renewable energy projects.

First, the government of Alberta created the Alberta Indigenous Opportunities Corporation (AIOC) in 2019. AIOC provides financial backing for Indigenous groups to invest in natural resource projects, including renewable energy. AIOC uses up to \$3 billion in loan guarantees to facilitate easier access to funding, secure more favorable loan terms, and lower borrowing costs (14).

Summary of Projects Supported by AIOC Loan Guarantees

Number	Date	Project Name	Project Type	Loan Guarantee Amount (CAD)
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1	September 2020	Cascade Power Project	Natural Gas-fired Power Plant	\$93 million
2	April 2021	Lindbergh Co-Generation Facility	Cogeneration Facility	\$25 million
3	November 2021	Northern Courier Project	Pipeline	\$40 million
4	September 2022	Athabasca Trunkline Project	Liquids Pipelines	\$250 million
5	July 2023	Access NGL Transportation System	NGL Pipeline	\$103 million
6	December 2023	Clearwater Midstream Assets	Oil & Gas Midstream Facility	\$150 million
7	December 2023	Wembley Gas Plant Project	Cogeneration Facility	\$20.5 million
8	September 2024	Clearwater Midstream Project Expansion	Oil & Gas Midstream Facility	\$44.9 million
9	March 2025	Duchess Solar Project	Renewable Energy (solar)	\$22 million
Total Amount				\$748.5 million

Table 1. Summary of Projects Supported by AIOC Loan Guarantees. Since its launch in 2019, the AIOC has supported nine project investments involving 42 distinct Indigenous communities in Alberta, providing a total of over \$748 million in loan guarantees (14).

Also, the Government of Alberta established the Alberta Indigenous Green Energy Development Program (AIGEDP) in 2017 as part of the province's Climate Leadership Plan.

AIGEDP helps Alberta Indigenous communities and organizations acquire an ownership stake in Alberta's rapidly expanding renewable energy sector. AIGEDP focuses on supporting the development of renewable energy generation projects (with a generation capacity above 1 megawatt (MW) (15). AIGEDP provides funding for both project development and implementation. For early-stage planning, communities can receive up to \$60,000 to see if a project is possible and up to \$550,000 to do more detailed studies and make business plans. For projects ready to be built, the program can cover all of the eligible costs (15).

Furthermore, in October 2016, the Government of Alberta announced the Alberta Indigenous Solar Program (AISP). AISP provides grants to Alberta Indigenous communities to assist with the installation of small-scale solar PV panel systems on facilities owned by Indigenous communities or organizations. After installing PV panel systems, Indigenous communities can generate their own energy and lower energy costs. The AISP offers funding for up to 80% of eligible expenses, with a maximum grant of \$200,000 per project (16).

In conclusion, Indigenous participation is essential to Alberta's renewable energy transition. Legal frameworks such as treaty rights, Section 35 of the Constitution Act, UNDRIP, and FPIC establish mandatory consultation, ensuring Indigenous Peoples are meaningfully involved in projects on their lands. Current participation models

include both equity-holding and non-equity forms. Furthermore, government initiatives such as the AIOC, AIGEDP, and AISP provide financial and technical support to strengthen this involvement.

CURRENT ISSUES IN INDIGENOUS PARTICIPATION IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

Although the Alberta government has established several organizations to support Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects, there are still many aspects of these partnerships that could be refined. In this section, we will discuss the current issues in Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects.

Legal and Regulatory Uncertainty

First, FPIC is not clearly established in Alberta, which results in legal and regulatory uncertainty regarding renewable energy projects involving Indigenous Peoples. Alberta has yet to fully embrace FPIC's requirement of "consent." This means that renewable energy projects may still proceed despite the concerns of Indigenous communities. The lack of explicit legal frameworks has created uncertainty for developers and Indigenous communities, making renewable energy projects in partnership with Indigenous Peoples less desirable for investment.

Another example of this legal uncertainty is the temporary pause in approvals for new renewable energy projects in Alberta from August 2023 to February 2024. This pause allowed the Alberta Utilities Commission (AUC) to review and update the regulatory process for renewable energy projects (17). However, this pause in renewable energy approvals created uncertainty for investors and practical challenges for both Indigenous communities and developers.

Limited Support Across the Renewable Energy project Lifecycle

Currently, Indigenous Peoples lack sufficient support in the following areas, which are essential to protecting their rights and benefits before, during, and after the implementation of renewable energy projects.

Lack of Guidance in Choosing Partnership Models

First, Indigenous Peoples are often not fully informed about which type of partnership to pursue in renewable energy projects. Currently, various models are available, including equity ownership, revenue sharing, employment and training programs that provide jobs and skills to community members, contracting opportunities for Indigenous businesses (such as construction and maintenance services), and land leases where developers pay rent or fees for the use of Indigenous lands. In recent years, however, equity ownership has become increasingly common, a sign that Indigenous communities are getting more involved in the project (14). As a result, Indigenous communities often require professional advice to determine the most suitable partnership model to pursue.

Lack of Guidance in Assessing Risk and Valuation

Indigenous communities often face significant challenges when assessing the risks of participating in renewable energy projects and the value they bring to these projects. However, many Indigenous communities lack access to the specialized financial and legal advice they need. This gap in capacity places them at a disadvantage during negotiations with developers or government partners, as they may struggle to articulate their value to the project or fully understand the potential risks involved. Due to this, Indigenous Peoples may end up with reduced equity shares and decision-making power in project partnerships.

Gaps in Securing Indigenous Consent

The process by which Indigenous Communities decide on “consent” for the implementation of renewable energy projects is varied. For instance, some Indigenous communities employ traditional governance methods of giving consent which means that the project can proceed as long as elders, clan leaders, and hereditary chiefs give their consent. In another form of giving consent, the elected chief and council pass a resolution to determine whether to proceed with the project. Additionally, some communities only grant consent when all members vote, which typically occurs for major projects with a broader scope. Finally, some communities use a mixed approach, where the council negotiates with external collaborators, but the community members vote to approve the final decision.

Lack of Standardized Agreement Templates

Another significant challenge is the absence of a standardized agreement template for renewable energy partnerships with Indigenous communities. Since most agreements are confidential, communities cannot easily compare terms, conditions, or benefits across different projects. Additionally, due to the lack of a standardized agreement template, Indigenous Peoples may not know which aspects to focus on during the negotiation process. This lack of transparency gives project developers and owners greater bargaining power and information, as Indigenous communities are more vulnerable to entering into deals that may undervalue their contributions or expose them to high, disproportionate risks.

Limited Access to Expert Knowledge

A further challenge lies in Indigenous Peoples’ lack of expert knowledge and technical capacity related to renewable energy projects. While Indigenous communities may be able to participate at the early stages of a project, the long-term success of these partnerships often depends on specialized expertise in management, operations, and maintenance once the project is completed.

Currently, many communities lack access to training in these areas, which limits their ability to participate actively in daily management and decision-making processes. This skills gap not only reduces the level of Indigenous involvement but also makes it harder to protect their rights and ensure that benefits of the project are distributed fairly over time.

In conclusion, legal and regulatory vagueness regarding FPIC, along with limited guidance support before, during, and after project implementation—such as little guidance on selecting partnership models and assessing risks and value, incomplete Indigenous consent before project execution, lack of standardized agreements, and limited access to technical expertise—are key issues in current Indigenous-involved renewable energy projects.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The challenges with current Indigenous partnerships in renewable energy projects were outlined in the previous section. In this section, we will propose policy recommendations to solve the issues outlined in the previous section and support Indigenous communities participation in renewable energy projects.

Embed FPIC in Project Approvals

At present, both federal and provincial governments, including in Alberta, operate under the principle of a “duty to consult,” which makes it mandatory for developers to engage with Indigenous communities but does not require developers to obtain their consent for project execution. This often leaves Indigenous Peoples in the position of being heard but not having real decision-making power.

Embedding Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) into renewable energy approvals would give Indigenous communities greater legal authority in these projects. FPIC ensures that communities provide explicit approval before a project begins, which guarantees that consent is fully informed and obtained in advance of project implementation. This approach reduces the risk of conflict or legal disputes and promotes equitable Indigenous participation in renewable energy projects. It also empowers Indigenous Peoples as active decision-makers of renewable energy projects rather than passive consultees. Furthermore, it reduces the likelihood of conflict and legal disputes by ensuring fair and meaningful collaboration from the outset. Importantly, adopting FPIC aligns Canadian policy with the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP), thereby reinforcing Canada’s human rights obligations.

Support System During Project Negotiation and Implementation

Even when Indigenous Peoples are included in renewable energy projects, many communities face systemic barriers that limit their ability to participate on equal terms. To address this, governments should establish a comprehensive support system that provides both financial and technical assistance before, during, and after project implementation. Key support measures include:

First, as Indigenous communities often lack access to expert advice, they require independent advisors who can assist with risk assessment, financial planning, and legal negotiations. Having access to these advisors will prevent Indigenous communities from entering into unfair or one-sided agreements.

Second, training programs that provide technical skills in renewable energy are important to help Indigenous Peoples stay involved over the long term. Some training programs include courses on solar panel installation and maintenance, wind turbine operation, and battery storage.

Finally, agreements should be standardized and made transparent by providing publicly available model contracts. This will ensure that communities have clear reference points when entering negotiations.

Government Support and Oversight After Project Completion

Government support should continue after a renewable energy project is built. Ongoing support and oversight are crucial to ensure long-term benefits for Indigenous communities. This includes regulatory oversight to guarantee transparent operations and adherence to fair partnership agreements, as well as continued training and technical support to build the skills necessary for project management and maintenance. By keeping Indigenous Peoples actively involved and ensuring equitable benefits, governments help ensure that renewable energy projects contribute to the process of reconciliation.

In conclusion, the above are policy recommendations that governments can consider adopting before, during, and after execution of renewable energy projects. First, FPIC should be embedded into project approvals to protect rights of Indigenous Peoples legally. Second, during project negotiation and implementation, Indigenous Peoples should be given greater access to professional advice, training programs, and standardized agreement templates. Third, government support should continue even after project completion to ensure that Indigenous communities remain actively involved in the project and also benefit equitably from their participation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper identified key issues within current Indigenous partnerships and proposed policy recommendations to address them. These key Issues include legal and regulatory uncertainty, limited support for choosing partnership models and assessing risks and value, lack of access to technical training in renewable energy, absence of standardized agreement templates, and incomplete Indigenous consent for projects. Suggested policy recommendations include embedding Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) in project approvals, providing independent advisory and technical support throughout negotiations and implementation, and maintaining post-construction oversight to protect benefits for Indigenous Peoples.

Ultimately, Alberta's renewable energy transition could engender economic independence, environmental stewardship and reconciliation with Indigenous Peoples. In addition, it demonstrates that a sustainable and resilient energy future is achievable, particularly when Indigenous Peoples are genuine partners involved in shaping it. Future research could focus on comparing how Indigenous participation in renewable energy is practiced across Alberta and other Canadian provinces, in order to identify more effective and inclusive policy solutions that strengthen Indigenous partnerships nationwide.

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